

MODERN METHODS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6496942>

Hikmatova Mohira Akmal qizi

*Teacher at Uzbekistan state World Languages University,
Tashkent city, Uzbekistan.*

Abstract: *This article is intended to give basic information about teaching by various specific methods and ways. The most essential aim of education is enhancing the quality of teaching that is completely crucial today. There are many important and innovative teaching methods that can be utilized in teaching and learning. In education system, there are interactive, innovative and interesting methods that can be conducted by teachers to emphasize on improving students' foreign language awareness. This paper can be helpful to get basic information related to teaching different languages.*

Key words: Teaching methods, intensive teaching, language learning, technical means, methodological literature.

There is a lot of work being done not only on teaching foreign languages, but also on finding and testing new methods of teaching all subjects. This is one of the most important issues facing education today. If in the past foreign language teaching was considered to be the study of this language system, in recent years the main focus of teaching has been to develop these students' foreign language skills. It should be noted that these goals in foreign language learning are not set by oneself or by others or individuals, but are closely related to changes in the sciences of linguistics and psychology and the social development of society. For example, consider the audiolingual method. The development of this method was influenced by changes in linguistics, that is, the structural flow. It includes the following factors:

- Teaching a foreign language should begin with teaching oral speech;
- Language learning is based on different structures, patterns of speech;
- Exercises should also be language-based exercises that require repeated repetition of language material;

- The choice of grammatical patterns and vocabulary should depend on the results of the comparison of the foreign language with the native language.

- Great attention to pronunciation is required. The main disadvantages of this method are the large number of mechanical exercises and the lack of real speech exercises. The founders of this method are Methodist scholars Ch. Fries and R. Lado. For example, Ch. Fries says that the main content of the initial stage should be the study of structures. It is important that grammar skills are based on this.

According to Ch. Fries and Lado, students should first remember the set of structures (sentences) used in oral speech. Then, based on these structures, new ideas need to be developed, that is, skills and abilities need to be developed. This is done through training exercises. Later, a new method began to emerge in the West. This was an audio-visual method. Its founders are Yugoslav Methodists P. Guberin and Frenchman Pierre Rimon, L. Gugenheim and others. This method is based on quick memorization of language (language material) by hearing and seeing. The main advantage of this method is that it requires the study of language material in relation to real-life situations. Language learning is based on seeing, listening and understanding. According to the authors of this method, it aims to study topics that are common in everyday life (for example, apartments, furniture, trade, etc.). They are mastered mainly on the basis of visual perception and extensive use of technical means. Much has been done and is being done in our country and abroad to intensify foreign language teaching. This has led to the development of new intensive methods. So what is an intensive method? How can it be understood?

Intensive teaching is the first meaning of the word to teach students to perform speaking activities in a foreign language in a short period of time. This is based on the students' internal psychological capacity and memory. (Leontev A. A. Kitaygorodskaya). Thus, the intensive method (or intensive) teaching has the following two characteristics: Organize a certain amount of educational material in a short period of time and carry out the corresponding foreign language speaking activity; Maximizing the use of all the resources (psychological capabilities) of personal memory, ie increasing the activity of students.

In recent years, more needs to be done to increase student engagement in the classroom. One of the most important tasks is to create an environment of verbal communication in order to increase the activity of students in the classroom, using the internal capabilities of personal

memory. The methods used by the teacher and the various visual aids should be aimed at this goal. The psychological state of verbal communication is one of the most important tasks in increasing the activity of students. E.I. Passov, one of the well-known Methodist scholars, says that the communicative approach used in modern foreign language teaching is a form of intensive teaching based on speech situations.

The intensive method was first developed in the early twentieth century on the basis of the "correct" method. Prof. According to E. I. Gez, "The right method has created a favorable environment and basis for intensive foreign language teaching." Some of the key aspects of the right method, such as interest in oral discourse, especially the choice of speech situations for dialogic speech, and the need to increase student engagement in the classroom, are the basis of some modern intensive methods. This is natural, because each new method retains the advantages of the previous method. In recent years, words denoting a new direction, such as audiolingual, audiovisual, hypnopedia, relaxation, suggestopedia, rhythmopedia, have become more common in the methodological literature. It should be noted that audiolingual and audiovisual methods cannot be used in intensive training. This is hampered by their principled nature of not relying on the use of the mother tongue, the abundance of learning, memorization and creative exercises by imitating the language. Hypnopedics, Relaxed Therapy - these methods only give good results in memorizing language material, but do not provide use in speech. That is why the well-known scientist prof. Gegechkori L.Sh. suggests that hypnopedia and relaxation should be considered as techniques that can be used in foreign language teaching because they are intended only to remember the information being conveyed. In recent years, much attention has been paid to the integration of research in pedagogy, psychology, social psychology, and medical sciences in the study of the individual as an object and the identification of all its creative potential. An important issue today is the focus on students' new thinking, creative thinking, and preparing them for life. This increases the need for a comprehensive study of the individual. Thus, the student's personality has become a central figure in the learning process. G. Lozanov is a psychotherapist, doctor of medical sciences, Bulgarian scientist - focused on the study of human internal reserves. He began to study three important factors:

1. Opening memory reserves;
2. To study the intellectual activity of the student;

3. Positive emotion, (loses the feeling of fatigue). (The role, authority of the teacher; the relationship between teacher and student; mutual trust, high level of motivation, the opening of the individual's internal reserve capacity. Admittedly, Lozanov's method includes: 1) in the study of a large number of speech units; 2) to develop students' ability to use language, vocabulary in the process of speaking a foreign language, to use the learned unit of speech in another situation; 3) creating high motivation to learn to read; 4) the presence of psychological barriers (shyness, fear, humanity) gives very good results in removing. It is noteworthy that Lozanov did not set himself the task of developing a method of teaching a foreign language. In the 60s and 70s, Lozanov's method was used in foreign language learning. At present, scientists and methodologists have developed their own way of combining intensive methods with the "Right-Practical" method used in our country. He said that it is expedient to apply only some principles of this method (Lozanov).

In short, some features of this or that intensive course can be applied in the process of teaching in a foreign language higher education system. It is designed to make a person more active in the learning process. The term "method" is widely used as a general theory of educational teaching. Didactics interprets the term "method" in terms of the way teachers and students work to gain knowledge, skills, attitudes, and opportunities for teachers. General teaching methods have been developed for the subjects that teach the basics of science. The methodology of teaching a foreign language is developed in the methodology, taking into account the specifics of the subject.

It takes a long time to teach foreign language periods. In foreign language teaching methods, the term "method" has three main meanings. First, a whole line in the history of methodology (translation method, correct method, comparative method, mixed method); Second, the training system that is part of the above; Third, the way teachers and students interact. (Methods of acquaintance, practice and application). In the history of foreign language teaching, the first and second methods are called "historical" methods, and the third is called "process expression". Historically, the methods have been grouped into four groups, with the addition of the words "translation", "correct (or without translation)", "comparative", "mixed" to their names, so that the foreign language o ' all the methods in the centuries-old history of the unit are grouped into four categories. A brief analysis of each of them is required, because in the first method, some of their features are used in a certain way.

In conclusion, this research has shown that interactive teaching methods can improve the quality of teaching. The main problem is how to get more interested and skilled in-service teachers. Our further activities will be concentrated not only on our university students and pre-service teachers but also on in-service teachers to improve their knowledge about the methods mentioned above.

REFERENCES:

1. J. Jalolov. English Teaching Methods, Teacher Publishing House. Tashkent.
2. K voprosu ob istorii razvitiya intensivnyx metodov zarubejnom. Methods of intensive training in foreign languages. Izd. MGPIIYa, «Visshaya shkola» 3, 1977.
3. G. Lozanov Sushchnost istorii i eksperimentalnye perspektivy redagogicheskoy sistemy pri obuchenii inostrannym yazykam. Izd. MGPIIYa, «Vysshaya shkola» 3, 1977.
4. G. A. Kitaygorodskaya. Methods of intensive training in foreign languages. Moscow, Vysshaya Shkola
5. Method of prepostovaniya inostrannix yazikov zarubejom. Moscow, "Progress" 1967.
6. Narimanova J.Y The Role of Teachers' Cultural Awareness in Preparing To Work With Multicultural Students. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations (ISSN – 2689-100x) Published: September 18, 2020. P: 172-181.
1. 7. Narimanova J.Y. Development of intercultural communicative competence of students in the study of foreign language. Молодой учёный. Международный научный журнал. 2018. 71-72-73- бетлар.
7. Narimanova J.Y. Raising EFL Students" Intercultural Communication through Short Stories. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 4, Issue 7, July – 2020, Pages: 24-32